

AGE OF PERALKALINE AND ALKALINE MAGMATISM OF THE OSSA-MORENA ZONE: TIME CONSTRAINTS ON THE LOWER PALEOZOIC RIFTING OF THE NORTHERN MARGIN OF WEST GONDWANA

1 The Ossa-Morena Zone in SW Iberia represents a section of the northern margin of West Gondwana that retains a record of rifting that led to the opening of the Rheic Ocean in the early Paleozoic. The oldest rocks exposed in the Ossa Morena Zone constitute a thick succession of greywackes, quartzwackes, pelites, black cherts, mafic volcanic rocks, and a few layers of limestone (Serie Negra succession) and they have been interpreted as the infill of a back-arc basin formed along the northern margin of West Gondwana during the Ediacaran (Eguiluz et al., 2000; Pereira et al., 2006). This series is unconformably overlain by early Cambrian sedimentary rocks (Liñán and Quesada, 1990), which are the base of a rift sequence starting with sandstones, pelites and conglomerates, followed by siliciclastics and carbonates, and then covered by pelites and sandstones (Sánchez-García et al., 2003, 2010). Locally, the deposition of carbonates dominated most of the Cambrian sequence. The Cambrian rift sequence contains volcanic rocks concentrated at two main stratigraphic levels. The lower level contains only felsic volcanic and volcanoclastic rocks of calc-alkaline affinity, and is found as interbedded layers within the base of the Cambrian succession (Sánchez-García et al., 2003, 2008). Felsic rocks of this event were dated at c. 530–526 Ma (Chichorro et al., 2008; Sánchez-García et al., 2008; Pereira et al., 2011). Rhyolites may occur locally in an upper stratigraphic position, and have been dated at c. 522 Ma and 517–515 Ma (Chichorro et al., 2008; Sánchez-García et al., 2008). Culminating the rift sequence, there is a volcanic-sedimentary complex composed of slates, sandstones and a few conglomerates interbedded with massive bimodal volcanic rocks of middle Cambrian age (c. 505–502 Ma; Sánchez-García et al., 2003; Pereira et al., 2004, 2007; Chichorro et al., 2008). The Cambrian series of the Ossa Morena Zone were subjected to uplift, tilting, erosion and/or non-deposition during and after sedimentation (Liñán and Quesada, 1990).

3 In Iberia, peralkaline and alkaline magmatism is associated with the development of highly-subsident early Paleozoic sedimentary basins (von Raumer and Stampfli, 2008), ring dikes and normal faults (Galindo, 1989; Díez Fernández and Martínez Catalán, 2009), and chemical compositions indicating a significant mantle input (Mata and Munhá, 1986, 1990; Galindo, 1989; Galindo et al., 1990; Sánchez-García et al., 2003). These features implicate an extensional setting of intra-continental rifting during the generation of the magmas from which peralkaline and alkaline rocks derived. Since the peralkaline/alkaline suite intrudes both the Ediacaran (Serie Negra) and the Cambrian rift sequence, dating of its representative members is essential to constrain the timing of lithosphere extension as well as that of the arrival of deeply-sourced magmas to the upper crust.

4 Three rock samples were collected to perform U-Pb LA-MC-ICP-MS analysis on zircon. Two samples of strongly sheared peralkaline (PAL-1) and alkaline (PAL-2) orthogneisses were collected close to the northern boundary of the Ossa Morena Zone. A third peralkaline syenite (PAL-3) was collected from the Elvas massif. The peralkaline rocks of this massif shows spatial and chemical relationships with large bodies of mafic rocks (Carrilho Lopes et al., 1996). Previous petrographic and chemical work classified the protoliths of these rocks as alkaline/peralkaline syenites, with more than 65% of the rock constituted by feldspar and with riebeckite/aegirine or hastingsite (Teixeira and Assunção, 1958; Gonçalves and Assunção, 1970; Coelho and Gonçalves, 1971; Carrilho Lopes et al., 1996). These rocks can be classified as subsolvus syenites due to the presence of two types of alkali feldspar (K and Na).

2 A magmatic suite of mafic and felsic (mostly alkaline) rocks occur along the northern boundary of the Ossa-Morena zone. The successions of the Ossa Morena Zone, particularly the Serie Negra, are intruded by a number of peralkaline and alkaline granitoids. In the Coimbra-Cordoba shear zone those igneous rocks occur as elongate massifs of weakly foliated granitoids or as narrow bands of orthogneiss alternating with schists and paragneisses due to the intense deformation and metamorphism that took place during the Variscan Orogeny (Gonçalves and Assunção, 1970; Gonçalves, 1971; Gonçalves and Fernandes, 1973; Gonçalves et al., 1975)

5 The crystallization ages of the syenites obtained in this work span c. 20 m.y., from c. 490 Ma (sample PAL-3, Elvas pluton) to c. 470 Ma (PAL-2, Arronches Lineaments), and show an apparent return period of c. 10 m.y. (c. 479 Ma, sample PAL-1, Figueira de Cima - Cevadais Lineament). Consequently, despite the compositional differences there may be among the different rock bodies, the ages of the peralkaline and alkaline magmatism of the Ossa-Morena Zone as a whole are compatible with a persistent tensional regime during the Cambrian-Ordovician transition. Moreover, such magmatism followed a period of continental extension starting at c. 530–526 Ma (Romeo et al., 2006; Chichorro et al., 2008; Sánchez-García et al., 2003, 2008; Pereira et al., 2006, 2011). Therefore, the Ossa-Morena Zone was subjected to long-lived crustal extension since the cessation of the subduction-related magmatic activity of the Cadomian arc-system (i.e. for a minimum of about 60 m.y. from c. 530 to c. 470 Ma).

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